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**EFFECT OF CONSTRUCTIVIST TEACHING APPROACH ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE AND RETENTION IN ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE
WORKS TRADE IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN TARABA STATE**

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the effect of the constructivist approach on students' academic performance and retention in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade in Technical Colleges in Taraba State. The study was guided by three research questions. The study adopted a pre-test – post-test non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental research design and an opinion survey research design. The population of the study comprised the entire 200 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) Trade students in NTCII in the six Government Science and Technical College in Taraba State. The sample size for the study was 71 students. The instruments used for data collection was a 20-item multiple choice question covering four content areas in electrical installation and maintenance work trade. The instruments were validated by three experts, two from the department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University Yola and one from Government Science and Technical College Yola. The achievement test instrument (EIMWAT). The data were analyzed using the statistical mean, and standard deviation. Findings of the study include among others: There were no significant differences between the mean performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State; It was recommended among others that Technical Colleges should integrate the constructivist approach into their teaching strategies, as it significantly improves students' academic performance; Educators should undergo regular professional development programme on constructivist teaching strategies to effectively implement them in technical subjects; Schools should provide adequate instructional materials.

Keywords: Constructivist Approach, Academic Performance, Retention, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade

INTRODUCTION

The primary purpose of teaching at any level of education is to bring a fundamental change in the learner. To facilitate the process of knowledge transmission, teachers are expected to apply appropriate teaching methods that best suit specific objectives and level exit outcomes. In the traditional epoch, many teaching practitioners widely apply teacher-centered methods to impart knowledge to learner's comparative to student-centered methods (Tebabal & Kahssay, 2020). These days, questions about the effectiveness of teaching methods on student learning have consistently raised considerable interest in the

field of technical educational research. Moreover, research on teaching and learning constantly endeavor to examine the extent to which different teaching methods enhance growth in student learning (Chang, 2017). Omiko (2017) observed that the changes in education curriculum in recent years has led to consequent shift of emphasis from content to processes of teaching; from the traditional chalk and talk (lecture) method to modern methods of teaching science such as activity-oriented method of instruction, laboratory method, concept-mapping, demonstration method, enquiry method and constructivist method among others. According to Ootobo (2020) there is a shift in the teaching paradigm from teacher-centered to student-centered in Government Science and Technical Colleges across Nigeria. Teaching methods in technical colleges can be classified as a teacher-centered method, student-centered method, and student-teacher interaction methods. Under the teacher-centered method of instruction, students simply obtain information from the teacher without building their engagement level with the subject being taught. Elvis (2021) opined that the teacher-centered method of teaching is less practical, more theoretical, and memorizing. It does not apply activity-based learning to encourage students to solve real-life problems based on applied knowledge. In the teacher-centered method of teaching, the teacher controls the transmission and sharing of knowledge, the teacher attempts to maximize the delivery of information while minimizing time and effort.

Constructivists' instructional approach is student-driven, where teachers only serve as guides, which enable learners to construct their understanding of information as they work with concepts and think about their processes. In this instructional approach students redefine, reorganize, elaborate, and change their initial concepts through interaction with the environment as well as other individuals. The constructivist instructional approach recognizes that learners build new ideas on top of their conceptual understanding, bring their prior knowledge and experience to the text, and from there, construct their knowledge (Musa & Hassan, 2022). Ndubusi (2017) emphasized that students learn best when they are active and seek solutions for themselves through interacting and dialoguing with one another. This is because dialogue among students is an important strategy for motivating and encouraging students to construct new knowledge. In furtherance of Ndubusi's view, see the constructivist instructional approach to teaching as innovative and interactive, because it involves other desirable active teaching methods such as inquiry teaching method, project-based teaching method, and cooperative teaching method amongst others that explores students' ability by teaching.

According to Anbessa (2020) the demonstration method is one in which the teacher shows how something is done practically or displays something for the learner to observe with the aim of being able to perform the same activity afterwards it may be supplemented with chalk board work. Demonstration method of teaching is a traditional strategy used in technical colleges and in teacher training colleges. Farooq went further to state that the demonstration strategy focuses to achieve psychomotor and cognitive objectives. The ability of students to recall or retain learned tasks is a critical component of the educational process, deeply influencing their academic performance and long-term learning outcomes. Retention involves the process by which information is encoded, stored, and later retrieved from memory. Effective retention is often linked to several factors, including the quality of instruction, the frequency and methods of review, and the students' engagement with the material. Studies have shown that active learning techniques, such as spaced repetition, collaborative learning, and the application of knowledge in practical contexts, significantly enhance retention rates (Dunlosky et al., 2013). Additionally, the use of mnemonic devices and multimedia resources can aid in strengthening memory by making learning experiences more vivid and contextually rich. Moreover, the cognitive load theory suggests that retention is optimized when instructional materials are designed to reduce unnecessary cognitive load, allowing students to allocate more mental resources to the processing and understanding of new information. According to Mayer (2017), a multi-faceted approach that combines

cognitive strategies, appropriate instructional design, and consideration of the learners' psychological and physical well-being is essential for maximizing retention of learned tasks. Retention has a greater influence in academic achievement of students. According to Umar (2019) retention is defined as the ability of the memory to store information which can be recalled at interval of weeks, months or even years when exposed to series of instructions.

Gender issues in Government Science and Technical Colleges have also assumed prominence in students' academic performance and retention discourse. It has been documented that disparity exists between male and female students. According to Dania (2021) gender disparity were found to be negatively correlated, women are not enjoying social, mental, education and professional status equal to their male counterparts. In some cases, boys had an edge over girls in academic performance. On the other hand, Ojikutu (2018) reported that differences in the academic performance of male and female students does not exist. However, Shodeinde (2021) opined that it is possible that biological, psychological, and personal differences between boys and girls can be a factor when considering strategies for teaching them cum academic performance. Bigelow and Zhou (2016) asserted that in students' academic performance and retention, motivation and sustenance of the learners' interest are vital.

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) is a trade subject offered at the National Technical Certificate (NTC) level in Government Science and Technical College that is geared toward equipping its beneficiaries with knowledge and skills in electrical installation and maintenance practice at the craftsmen level. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016), the philosophy behind the establishment of the National Technical Certificate (NTC) program in Nigeria is to train Technical College Students with the necessary knowledge and skills that could lead to the production of craft men and other skilled personnel who could fill up vacancies of craft level personnel in Nigeria's industrial and business sector. EIMW course is run by the Government Science and Technical College which has been accredited by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and examined by the National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB). Different teaching methods exposed students to active learning in modern techniques that improve teaching and learning in classroom which involve the use of technology paved way for learner's centre strategy, and run away from the traditional method of transferring knowledge; which is the lecture method where the lecturer read out to the students and allow them to take down notes (Tumba & Chinda, 2014). The present situation of unemployment among products of technical and vocational schools is an indication that they are not well trained by their teachers to keep consonance with the dynamic nature of technological development (Fagge, 2017).

Academic achievement is a learning outcome that determines the extent to which a student has realized their educational goal and can be measured by many form of assessment technique. Mustapha (2016) state that students' academic achievement is closely related and influenced by so many factors that include among others school environment, learner's interest, mental ability, availability of facilities and instructional strategies used by teachers. He also opined that instructional strategy in fact is the most influential of all the factors regarding students' achievement. The basis for achieving the goals of teaching and learning in technical and vocational education is to acquaint students with scientific skills, knowledge and enhances their interest in practical skills for self-reliance. Kumazhege and Abdulhamid (2020) state that Academic achievement can be moderated by some factors such as; teaching method, teacher qualification and personality, students' readiness, learning environment, facilities and equipment for the learning to take place. Tella, *et al.* (2019) advised that the choice of any instructional approach or media to teach a given curriculum content in Government Science and Technical Colleges should be determined by the effectiveness of the preferred approach in improving learning achievement of students.

Ajelabi (2016) stated that the effectiveness of any instructional method is the ability of the given instructional method to achieve the maximum behavioral objectives of the lesson it is used to teach with minimum time, effort and other resources. Along this assertion therefore, this study set out to determine the effect of constructivist teaching method on students' academic performance, interest and retention in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) is a vital trade in technical colleges that equips students with practical skills required for employment, self-reliance, and technological advancement. However, evidence from classroom observations and students' performance records in Taraba State reveals that many students still perform poorly, show low interest, and have difficulty retaining knowledge in EIMW. Otopo (2020) observed that among other factors responsible for high failure rate of technical college students in the NABTEB examinations, particularly in the main trades is the poor teaching methods adopted by trade teachers in the Government Science and Technical Colleges. Moreover, it has been discovered by Bello (2017) and Ukwungwu (2018) that the persistent poor academic performance in technical subjects may be a result of inappropriate teaching methods adopted by trade teachers.

The consequences of not addressing this problem are that, it will be very difficult to teachers of EIMW to explore student-centered approaches to teaching that are relevant to the present contemporary teaching and learning (either constructivist or demonstration teaching methods) is more effective than the other in the teaching the subject. If appropriate teaching methods are not carefully selected and used to teach concepts as contained in EIMW trade module, EIMW trade students would not only lack the understanding and confidence needed but also would continue to perform poorly in examinations and workplaces. There is therefore the need to determine the effect of the constructivist teaching method on students' academic performance, and retention in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study sought to determine:

1. The mean academic performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.
2. The mean academic performance of students based on gender taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.
3. The mean academic retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided study:

1. The mean academic performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.
2. The mean academic performance of students based on gender taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.
3. The mean academic retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study was hinged on Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory (1967). Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory argues that learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas or concepts based on current/past knowledge. The theory states that learning is a process in which the learner can build on present and previous information through practice and activity. Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works is one of the trades offered in Technical Colleges. It is a Vocational trade that exposes students to skills.

According to Owoh and Ogwa (2019) Electrical Installation and Maintenance Practice is a program introduced for students to acquire practical skills in electrical works such as maintenance of electrical systems and circuits, electrical Installation, Inspection, and test procedures. Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade are expected to test, diagnose, service, install, and completely repair any fault on electrical machines and equipment using the manufacturer's manual. However, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Trade aim to give training and impart the necessary skills leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians, and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant.

Constructivism is a theory of knowledge and knowing. Its roots can be traced to the writings of Dewey, Piaget, Bruner, and Vygotsky. The verb 'construct' comes from the Latin word 'constru ere' which means to arrange or give structure. Ongoing structuring processes are the conceptual heart of constructivism. Kant in Arioder et al., (2020) emphasized the power of patterns of our thinking and regarded ideas as regulative principles in our experiences. The principles guiding constructivism are: (1) EIMW trade learning should start with issues that students are actively involved in trying to construct meaning. (2) Meaning requires an understanding of EIMW trade concepts as wholes as well as parts that must be understood in the context of wholes. (3) The mental model that students perceive the world and assumptions used to support them should be understood. (4) The purpose of learning is for individuals to construct their own meaning, not just memory of the right answer or someone else meaning. (5) A lecture method is an oral presentation of information by the instructor or teacher. Lecture is the method of passing factual information which include principles, concepts, ideas and theoretical knowledge about a given topic.

Lecture method has been in use as a teaching method for long. In lecture method student are perceived receivers of Information process therefore there not involved in learning process. A lecture is a narrative technique of delivering verbally a body of knowledge. The lecture method involves a formal discourse or exposition in a subject matter to attain stated instructional objectives, the teacher does the talking while the learners listen and occasionally take notes (Gholami et al., 2016). As an educator, this researcher has always been fascinated by the relationship between teaching methods and students' academic performance; especially when it comes to application in the context of 21st century education. It seems that there is something in teaching that opens the gate of learning. Successful learning indeed depends on various factors that are not all teacher-related, but the methods that a teacher uses continue to play an important role in student learning and academic performance. The challenges that educators face in the 21st century is so diverse that using better teaching methods is more crucial now than ever before.

Retention plays a pertinent role when it comes to the effective or correct application of whatever a pupil or student has learned. This is because a student retrieves the information, he/she has retained in his/her memory when the need arises (maybe during a test or examination). So, what has been learned and assimilated by the students can be measured by their ability to answer questions given to them in either test or examination (Uchegbue & Amalu, 2020). The aim of teaching

and learning all concepts in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade is making use of different teaching strategy and resource materials to establish a behavioral object and make learning more meaningful; this is the ultimate goal.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a pre-test – post-test non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental research design and an opinion survey research design. Olayiwola (2020) asserted that quasi-experimental design investigates possible cause and effect as well as relationship between two or more variables by the application of treatment which cannot be resolve by description or observation. According to Cohen, et al. (2019), quasi-experimental design is employed only when randomization was not possible and it is typically easier to set up than real experimental design. Similarly, to use a natural classroom setting for experimental research without random assignment, a nonequivalent group design of Quasi-experimental is considered more appropriate. Taraba State is located in the northeastern part of Nigeria. Geographically, it lies approximately between latitudes 6°30'N and 9°36'N, and longitudes 9°10'E and 11°50'E. The state shares borders with six Nigerian states: Nasarawa to the west, Benue to the southwest, Plateau to the northwest, Gombe to the north, Bauchi to the northeast, and Adamawa to the east. The population of the study comprised the entire 200 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) Trade students in NTCII as of 2024/ 2025 academic session in the six Government Science and Technical College in Taraba State. The sample for the study was intact classes of NTC II EIMWT in GSTC Karim Lamido and GSTC Jalingo with Karim Lamido having 29 students and Jalingo having 42 students. The researcher used the entire population of NTCII EIMW students of the two schools (71 students) as a sample size for the study as the population in the classes is manageable. The instruments for data collection were developed by the researcher. It was called the “Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Achievement Test (EIMWAT)”. The EIMWAT consisted of twenty multiple-choice items with four options (A, B, C and D) drawn from the topics that were taught under the Machine winding Module. The instrument was subjected to both content and face validation by three experts validates. To establish the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested on NTC II EIMW students of GSTC, Yola, Adamawa State, which is not part of the study area. This enabled the researcher to determine the workability of the instruments. Person Moment Correlation and Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of EIMWAT of which 0.85 were obtained. Data for this study was be analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. Mean statistics was be used to answer the research questions.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the mean academic performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

Table 1: Mean Academic Performance of Students Taught EIMW Using the Constructivist Approach and Demonstration Teaching Methods

Teaching Methods	Pre-test Scores of Students			Post-test Scores of Students		MG
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Constructivist	42	30.63	8.60	77.50	18.97	46.87
Demonstration	29	31.48	8.00	75.97	22.53	44.49
Mean Difference				1.53		

KEY: N = Number of Students in a Group, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, SD = Standard Deviation, M = Mead Difference, MG = Mean Gain, TM = Teaching Method

Note: Mean Gain = Post-Test Scores Minus Pre-Test Scores

Mean Difference = Post-Test Score of Constructivist Approach Minus Pre-Test Score of Demonstration TM

Table 1 shows the mean academic performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method. The constructivist group had a pre-test mean score of 30.63 with a standard deviation of 8.60 and a post-test mean score of 77.50 with a standard deviation of 18.97, resulting in a mean gain of 46.87. The demonstration group recorded a slightly higher pre-test mean score of 31.48 (SD = 8.00) but a lower post-test mean score of 75.97 (SD = 22.53), giving a mean gain of 44.49. The mean difference between the post-test scores of the two groups was 1.53 in favour of the constructivist approach. This indicates that although both teaching methods improved students' academic performance, the constructivist approach resulted in a higher mean gain compared to the demonstration method.

Research Question 2: What is the mean academic performance of students based on gender taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

Table 2: Mean Academic Performance of Students Taught EIMW Using the Constructivist Approach Demonstration Teaching Method

Teaching Methods	Gender	Post-test Scores of Students		
		\bar{x}	SD	MD
Constructivist Approach	Male	75.38	21.44	3.18
	Female	72.20	4.55	
Demonstration	Male	72.07	15.54	6.57
	Female	65.50	10.61	

KEY: *N* = Number of Students in a Group, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *MD* = Mead Difference

Note: Mean Difference = Post-Test Scores of Male Minus Post-Test Scores of Females.

Table 2 presents the mean academic performance of male and female students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods. For the constructivist approach, male students obtained a post-test mean score of 75.38 with a standard deviation of 21.44, while female students had a mean score of 72.20 with a standard deviation of 4.55, resulting in a mean difference of 3.18 in favour of males. Under the demonstration method, male students recorded a mean score of 72.07 (SD = 15.54), whereas female students had a mean score of 65.50 (SD = 10.61), producing a mean difference of 6.57, also in favour of males. The results indicate that male students performed better than their female counterparts in both teaching methods, with the performance gap being wider in the demonstration method than in the constructivist approach.

Research Question 3: What are the mean retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods in Technical Colleges in Taraba State.

Table 3: Mean Retention Scores of Students Taught EIMW Using the Constructivist Approach and Demonstration Teaching Methods

Teaching Methods	N	Post-test Scores of Students		Retention Scores of Students		MG
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Constructivist	42	77.50	18.97	68.24	24.26	-9.26
Demonstration	29	75.97	22.53	61.07	24.24	-14.90
Mean Difference				7.17		

KEY: *N* = Number of Students in a Group, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *M* = Mead Difference, *MG* = Mean Gain, *TM* = Teaching Method

Note: Mean Gain = Retention Scores Minus Post-Test Score

Mean Difference = Retention Scores of Constructivist Approach Minus Post-Test Score of Demonstration TM

Table 3 shows the mean retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods. For the constructivist group, the post-test mean score was 77.50 (SD = 18.97), while the retention mean score decreased to 68.24 (SD = 24.26), giving a mean loss of -9.26. For the demonstration group, the post-test mean score was 75.97 (SD = 22.53), which dropped to a retention mean score of 61.07 (SD = 24.24), resulting in a mean loss of -14.90. The mean difference in retention between the two groups was 7.17 in favour of the constructivist approach. This implies that while both groups experienced a decline in scores from post-test to retention test, students taught with the constructivist approach retained knowledge better than those taught with the demonstration method.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

This study found out that the mean academic performance of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State. The result shows the mean retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods. For the constructivist group, the post-test mean score was 77.50 (SD = 18.97), while the retention mean score decreased to 68.24 (SD = 24.26), giving a mean loss of -9.26. For the demonstration group, the post-test mean score was 75.97 (SD = 22.53), which dropped to a retention mean score of 61.07 (SD = 24.24), resulting in a mean loss of -14.90. The mean difference in retention between the two groups was 7.17 in favour of the constructivist approach. This implies that while both groups experienced a decline in scores from post-test to retention test, students taught with the constructivist approach retained knowledge better than those taught with the demonstration method. According to Owoh and Ogwa (2019) Electrical Installation and Maintenance Practice is a program introduced for students to acquire practical skills in electrical works such as maintenance of electrical systems and circuits, electrical Installation, Inspection, and test procedures. Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade are expected to test, diagnose, service, install, and completely repair any fault on electrical machines and equipment using the manufacturer's manual. However, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Trade aim to give training and impart the necessary skills leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians, and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant.

This study also found out the mean academic performance of students based on gender taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State. The result presents the mean academic performance of male and female students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods. For the constructivist approach, male students obtained a post-test mean score of 75.38 with a standard deviation of 21.44, while female students had a mean score of 72.20 with a standard deviation of 4.55, resulting in a mean difference of 3.18 in favour of males. Under the demonstration method, male students recorded a mean score of 72.07 (SD = 15.54), whereas female students had a mean score of 65.50 (SD = 10.61), producing a mean difference of 6.57, also in favour of males. The results indicate that male students performed better than their female counterparts in both teaching methods, with the performance gap being wider in the demonstration method than in the constructivist approach. Constructivism is a theory of knowledge and knowing. Its roots can be traced to the writings of Dewey, Piaget, Brunner, and Vygotsky. The verb 'construct' comes from the Latin word 'constru ere' which means to arrange or give structure. Ongoing structuring processes are the conceptual heart of constructivism. Kant in Arioder et al., (2020) emphasized the power of patterns of our thinking and regarded ideas

as regulative principles in our experiences. The principles guiding constructivism are: EIMW trade learning should start with issues that students are actively involved in trying to construct meaning. Meaning requires an understanding of EIMW trade concepts as wholes as well as parts that must be understood in the context of wholes. And the mental model that students perceive the world and assumptions used to support them should be understood. Etc. Lecture method has been in use as a teaching method for long. In lecture method student are perceived receivers of Information process therefore there not involved in learning process. A lecture is a narrative technique of delivering verbally a body of knowledge. The lecture method involves a formal discourse or exposition in a subject matter to attain stated instructional objectives, the teacher does the talking while the learners listen and occasionally take notes (Gholami et al., 2016).

This study also found out that the mean academic retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching method in Technical Colleges in Taraba State. shows the mean retention scores of students taught Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) using the constructivist approach and demonstration teaching methods. For the constructivist group, the post-test mean score was 77.50 (SD = 18.97), while the retention mean score decreased to 68.24 (SD = 24.26), giving a mean loss of -9.26. For the demonstration group, the post-test mean score was 75.97 (SD = 22.53), which dropped to a retention mean score of 61.07 (SD = 24.24), resulting in a mean loss of -14.90. The mean difference in retention between the two groups was 7.17 in favour of the constructivist approach. This implies that while both groups experienced a decline in scores from post-test to retention test, students taught with the constructivist approach retained knowledge better than those taught with the demonstration method. Retention plays a pertinent role when it comes to the effective or correct application of whatever a pupil or student has learned. This is because a student retrieves the information, he/she has retained in his/her memory when the need arises (maybe during a test or examination). So, what has been learned and assimilated by the students can be measured by their ability to answer questions given to them in either test or examination (Uchegbue & Amalu, 2020). The aim of teaching and learning all concepts in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade is making use of different teaching strategy and resource materials to establish a behavioral object and make learning more meaningful; this is the ultimate goal.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the effect of the constructivist approach on students' academic performance and retention in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) trade in Technical Colleges in Taraba State. The findings revealed that students taught using the constructivist approach demonstrated significant improvements in academic performance compared to their pre-test scores. Additionally, both male and female students benefited equally from the constructivist approach, as no significant differences were observed in their performance or retention levels. The study also established that students retained knowledge effectively, as indicated by the minimal difference between post-test and retention test scores. Based on these findings, the study concludes that the constructivist approach is an effective instructional method for enhancing students' academic achievement in technical education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations are made to enhance the teaching and learning of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works in Technical Colleges in Taraba State:

1. Technical Colleges should integrate the constructivist approach into their teaching strategies, as it significantly improves students' academic performance.

2. Schools should provide adequate instructional materials such as simulation tools, project-based learning kits, and problem-solving activities that align with constructivist principles.
3. While the constructivist approach has proven effective, the demonstration method should also be maintained as it leads to notable academic gains, particularly in skill-based learning.

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